

Soil Organic Matter Composition of Arenosols in Western Rhodopes Mountain, Bulgaria

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Abstract

The paper studies soil organic matter in sandy soils from Western Rhodopes region, which fall within the territory of Pazardzhik district of the South central planning region in Bulgaria. Brief information on the morphological characteristics of the soils established so far and their initial studies are presented. The composition of soil organic matter is determined by analysing its extractable (soluble) fractions and insoluble residue. The humus content of studied soils is discussed by comparison with soils of the same soil type and those with similar stage of development of soil-forming processes. The state of soil organic matter is evaluated according to various indicators related to the degree of humification, the state of humic acids and the type of humus in surface horizons.

Key words: Sandy soils, soil organic matter, humic acids, fulvic acid.

Introduction

In Bulgaria, the Arenosols are distributed in plains and hilly areas by the Black Sea coast and territories near the Danube River (Atanassova et al., 2013; Andreeva et al., 2016). Their predominant sand fraction was also found in soils from the terrace of Maritsa River, Plovdiv (Angelov & Vasileva, 2022), as well as in mountainous areas of the Western Rhodopes, Bulgaria (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023).

The Arenosols represent sandy azonal soils with different vegetation and relatively poorly developed soil profile (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). To a large extent, this is due to the predominant sandy fraction, determining the weak water-holding capacity of the soils, their high water permeability (Sapundzhiev, 2026; Andreeva et al., 2016), but also their susceptibility to appearance of certain water repellency in the surface horizon, in the cases of the presence of various hydrophobic compounds (Atanassova et al., 2013).

Sandy soils are low in nutrients (FAO and ITPS, 2015). The soil formation in them is in initial stage (Gyurov & Artinova, 2015) due to the unfavourable conditions and low accumulation of organic matter (Andreeva et al., 2016), which is essential for the management of these soils (Yost & Hartemink, 2019). The state of soil organic matter in

sandy soils of the Bulgarian Black Sea coast is well studied (Kirilov, 2013), but in mountainous regions the research is still preliminary (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023).

The paper aim is to enrich the studies of Arenosols from mountainous regions of Bulgaria by characterizing the composition of soil organic matter.

Materials and Methods

Object of the study are soils from the region of the Western Rhodopes, which fall within the territory of the Pazardzhik District of the South central planning region in Bulgaria (Sapundzhiev & Mitreva, 2016; Regional administration Plovdiv, 2024). The soils are characterized by mechanical composition with predominant sand fraction and are established during a field trip by Hristov & Kirilov (2023) who study their morphological features in accordance with the Guidelines for soil description (Jahn et al., 2006) and conduct various laboratory analyses to determine diagnostic indicators in relation to soil classification. Hristov & Kirilov (2023) study 5 soil profiles and present data on their mechanical composition, carbon and nitrogen content, pH and physicochemical characteristics (sorption capacity, exchangeable cations, base saturation). As a result, the authors establish basic diagnostic characteristics of studied soils and classify them as Arenosols with the corresponding qualifiers according to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources – WRB (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015).

For the present paper aim, the collected soil samples are analysed for determination of soil organic matter composition using the modified method of Tyurin (Kononova, 1963; Filcheva & Tsadilas, 2002). Surface horizons are studied because the total carbon content at depth in most of the soil profiles has low values (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023) that are below the limit of measurement accuracy, similar to some Technosols (Ivanov, 2007).

The discussions of the humus state of soils are carried out in accordance with the values from the Bulgarian classification for humus indicators in soils according to Artinova (Gyurov & Artinova, 2001).

The humus content is determined by calculating the values of total carbon with coefficient 1.724 ($C \times 1.724 = \text{humus}$) (Kononova, 1963).

The degree of humification of organic matter is calculated based on the fraction of humic acids and total carbon content ($C_h : C_{\text{total}} \times 100 \%$), as indicated in the Artinova's classification (Gyurov & Artinova, 2001).

The type of humus is determined by the ratio between humic acids and fulvic acids, depending on the classification of Grishina and Orlov for humus indicators in soils (Orlov, 1985).

Results and Discussion

Arenosols are characterized by primitive soil profile (Atanassova et al., 2013) and poorly formed humus horizon (Gyurov & Artinova, 2015). These morphological features fully correspond to the studied soils, where the soil profile is of type A(AC) – AC – C with low thick humus horizon varying between 3 – 7 cm (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023). This defines soils as weakly organic, such as the Arenosols of the northeastern and northwestern regions of the Danube River Valley (Tsolova et al., 2018; Banov et al., 2018).

The data in table 1 present the results of the analysis carried out for establishment of the content and composition of soil organic matter in surface horizons of the soil profiles.

Table 1. Content and composition of soil organic matter in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes

Profile №, horizon and depth (cm)	Total C, %	Organic carbon, %								E ₄ /E ₆	
		Extracted with 0.1M Na ₄ P ₂ O ₇ +0.1M NaOH			C _h /C _f	Humic acids fractions		Unextracted organic C, %	Extracted C in 0.1 N H ₂ SO ₄		
		Total	Humic acids	Fulvic acids		Free and bound with R ₂ O ₃	Bound with Ca				
1. A 0-3 cm	11.80	<u>3.26</u> ^{a*}	<u>1.92</u>	<u>1.34</u>	1.43	<u>1.79</u>	<u>0.13</u>	<u>8.54</u>	<u>0.28</u>	6.58	6.67
2. A 0-3 cm	4.59	<u>1.11</u>	<u>0.64</u>	<u>0.47</u>	1.36	100.00	0.00	<u>3.48</u>	<u>0.05</u>	5.72	5.86
3. AC 0-2 cm	2.71	<u>0.86</u>	<u>0.44</u>	<u>0.42</u>	1.05	<u>0.42</u>	<u>0.02</u>	<u>1.85</u>	<u>0.05</u>	5.64	6.09
4. A 0-24 cm	0.80	<u>0.25</u>	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.09</u>	1.78	0.00	100.00	<u>0.55</u>	<u>0.03</u>	5.12	-
5. Ah 0-7 cm	1.96	<u>0.44</u>	<u>0.22</u>	<u>0.22</u>	1.00	100.00	0.00	<u>1.52</u>	<u>0.05</u>	4.70	6.62

*a – % of soil sample; b – % of total carbon content; c – % of humic acids content

Based on the amount of total carbon, the humus content varies from low to very high according to Artinova's Bulgarian classification of humus indicators in soils (Gyurov & Artinova, 2001) (figure 1). Its values are dependent on the developing vegetation and the presence of organic horizon in some soil profiles (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023), and no relationship with the thickness of humus-accumulative horizon is observed. Wide variations in the humus content are also characteristic of other soils such as Rankers and Rendzinas, which are part of general class of soils with poorly developed soil-forming process, in the Genetic classification of soils in Bulgaria (Teoharov, 2019a, b). However, this established range is not typical for all sandy soils, as the humus content of Arenosols from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast is low to very low (Kirilov et al., 2015). The probable reason for this differentiation is due to the conditions of soil formation related to soil-forming materials, altitude, climate and vegetation.

The humification of organic matter is medium to high depending on the content of humic acids according to Artinova (for Bulgarian soils) (Gyurov & Artinova, 2001) (figure 2). This soil characteristic of organic matter does not greatly distinguish the studied sandy soils from the Western Rhodopes from those along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, which have slightly thicker surface horizons, and where even soil profiles with very high humification of organic matter in the surface (0-12 cm, 0-15 cm) sod horizons is established (Kirilov, 2013).

Figure 1. Gradation of humus content in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes

Figure 2. Humification of organic matter in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes

It is noteworthy that the humic acids in studied soils are almost 100 % free and bound with R_2O_3 (table 1), which defines them as mobile (Shishkov & Filcheva, 2018). This may be related to the already found low values of calcium and magnesium in the composition of exchangeable cations (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023), since in soils with high base saturation, humic acids are 100 % bound with alkaline cations (Andreeva et al., 2011). An exception is profile 4, where humic acids are completely bound with calcium, but here the lowest total

carbon values is found (table 1). This soil horizon is also characterized by the lowest content of total nitrogen, as well as highly acid reaction (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023) (table 2), depending on the classification of soils according to pH values (Koynov et al., 1980).

Table 2. pH values and nitrogen content in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023)

Profile №	Horizon, Depth (cm)	pH (H ₂ O)	Total N (%)
1	A 0 – 3	5.9	0.45
2	A 0 – 3	5.6	0.19
3	A 0 – 2	5.6	0.17
4	AC 0 – 24	4.9	0.06
5	Ah 0 – 7	5.6	0.08

Humic acids have slightly higher amount compared to fulvic acids (figure 3). Their ratio determines the fulvic-humic type of humus in the surface horizons of all profiles, depending on the classification of Grishina and Orlov for humus indicators in soils (Orlov, 1985). This shows that for profiles 1, 2 and 4, humification processes prevail over those of mineralization, while for profiles 3 and 5, these processes are equalized, similar to the surface horizons of soils from urban forest parks (Zhiyanski et al., 2012).

Figure 3. Content of organic matter fractions (% of soil sample) and ratio in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes

The content of *aggressive fraction of fulvic acids* (Filcheva, 2007) is low in the studied soil samples. The insoluble fraction of organic carbon has greater ratio in the surface horizons of all studied soil profiles (Table 1), which may be related to the lack of suitable conditions for decomposition of plant residues (Kirilov et al., 2012).

The enrichment of humus with nitrogen in humus-accumulative horizons is very low to low depending on the humus indicators of soils according to Artinova (Gyurov & Artinova,

2001) (figure 4). In most of the subsurface horizons of studied soil profiles, this enrichment is also very low (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023). Exception is profile 4 where the C/N ratio determines medium enrichment of humus with nitrogen in the surface horizon (table 2). However, we will remind here the characteristics of this horizon related to the lowest carbon and nitrogen content and also the highly acid reaction of the environment (tables 1, 2), regardless of the developing grass vegetation and the distinctive morphologically established thickness (0-24 cm) (Hristov & Kirilov, 2023).

The optical density of humic acids (E4/E6) is average according to Artinova (2014) classification (table 1). These indicators of the humus condition of studied sandy soils have similar values in forest litter and humus-accumulative horizon of Brown forest soil (Cambisols) (Filcheva & Malinova, 2015). An exception is the surface horizon of profile 5, where the optical density compared to the total amount of humic acids is high (table 1). Similar results are found in the metamorphic horizon of the Cambisol, for which Filcheva & Malinova (2015) explain that in the first case (medium optical density) the humic acids are lower molecular, and in the second case (high optical density) their condensation is accelerated.

Figure 4. Enrichment of humus with nitrogen (according to C/N ratio) in surface horizons of studied Arenosols from the Western Rhodopes

Conclusions

The accumulation of humus in the surface horizons of studied sandy soils is not related to their morphologically determined thickness. The humification of organic matter is similar in soils of the same soil type, formed under different geological characteristics and climate conditions. The previously established physico-chemical characteristics of sandy soils influence the state of humic acids in the composition of soil organic matter.

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